

Women Mental Health and Well-Being

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Abstract

Mental health of women is the crucial part of total mental health of society. Depression and anxiety in women are twice as compared to men. A number of married women suffers from domestic violence and mental disorders. Mental health is the concept which is used to describe cognitive or emotional well-being of a person and absence of any mental disorder. Women are considered as backbone of any community hence it is the most important factor that women should have a very good mental health. There are various types of disorders faced by women like stress, anxiety, panic disorder, social anxiety, phobia etc., which adversely affects their mental health and overall performance. Sometimes biological, environmental or psychological factors play an important part in determining the mental health problems. Family member, society and government can play a crucial role in maintaining good mental health of women.

Introduction

A Good Mental health is the ability of human being which enables individuals to deal with the various stresses of life, it also enables them to realize their own abilities to learn well and work well, and contribute something worthy to their community. It helps every individual to develop their collective abilities to make decisions, build relationships and many more. Mental health is considered a basic human right. And it is essential for wellbeing of every person community and socio-economic development of the country. Mental health has various aspects which includes various mental disorders and psychosocial disabilities of the person. Person especially a woman having a good mental health condition is able to face various adverse conditions.

Mental health is the concept which is used to describe cognitive or emotional well-being of a person and absence of any mental disorder. Mental health increases the ability of any individual to enjoy life. It is a part of balance between life activities and efforts to achieve desired goals. Mental illness or disorder is described as unwillingness of psychological and behavioral pattern that is found in every individual and it is

the thought which causes stress or disability which is not expected as a part of normal development of any individual.

Objectives of paper

1. To explicate mental health problems faces by the women.
2. To suggest innovative ways for women to overcome from mental health problems

Research Methodology of this paper

The presented research paper is based on secondary sources. For this, observation, various reference texts, articles, secondary sources like internet sources have been used and content analysis technique has been used.

Importance of Women Mental health

A woman can play a vital role in overall development of society and country. From ancient period they are proving themselves as a valuable and important part of society which is incomplete without women. Its new age which is changing very rapidly and women from any society or country are facing various critical issues about their health which may be physical health, mental health or social health. New age is having various new issues which includes a very major issue of mental health of women. Women are considered as backbone of any community hence it is the most important factor that women should have a very good mental health.

Types of Mental health problems faced by women

Gender which contributes very seriously towards mental health and other health related issues. The morbidity which is an unhealthy mental state is more susceptible to women than men about many common mental health conditions. Women often found facing different challenges than men and they can experience various symptoms differently than men. There are various types of disorders faced by women which adversely affects their mental health and overall performance.

Women may experience various mental health conditions which can be different per person. While some men may act out differently in anger due to depression. It is believed that women are more likely to experience intoxication, sadness, and lack of motivation. They are found facing different mental health challenges which are very different from men and also have higher level of anxiety and depression, which are directly related to various physical health factors. Depression during menopause, Changes in hormones at specific age may lead to postpartum depression, or may experience premenstrual dysphonic disorder (PMDD).

Symptoms of mental disorders in women

There are various noteworthy symptoms which can be noted among women facing various mental disorders. Persistent sadness or feelings of hopelessness, finding it difficult to sleep or sleeping too much, gaining or losing weight, Misuse of drugs or alcoholic substances, Decreased everyday energy or feeling fatigue, sudden and extreme change in moods, Excessive fear or phobia, Seeing or hearing things in not in vicinity, Anger or irritability, excessive thinking about someone's behavior or unpleasant incidents, various types of Aches, headaches, or digestive problems without a clear reason, Low confidence level, total or partial Social withdrawal, Over caring or overthinking about common things, Thoughts or behaviors which effects on work, family, or social life, Crying for no reason or very minor reason, Noticeable changes in mood, energy, or appetite, negative thoughts of death or suicide or attempting it. These are common symptoms of mental disorders in women. As a supportive family member, it is the responsibility of every family member to take a care of mental health of women.

Reasons behind the mental health problems

Many times, women can't communicate and express their feeling with others, and may completely shut themselves down. They often feel helpless to express themselves to other family members or relatives. There are some causes that trigger mental health problems in women. Sometimes biological, environmental

or psychological factors play an important part in determining the mental health problems. Social or work pressure, social isolation, Family related problems, domestic violence Genetics, Stress, experience of scary and dangerous situations, Sedentary lifestyle, Past painful relationships, financial problems.

There are various factors that are related with women's mental health disorders. These factors affect their biological makeup and also adversely affect on their specific personal experiences as women in society. It is believed that women are on more discriminated side for their gender as compared to men. A women's life can be impacted by their mental health conditions it may impact on their ability to work, relationship participation in family or social life

Need of overcoming these problems

Mental health of women is the most important subject and should be taken into consideration with the subject of extremely preference. Mental health of women is associated with various mental conditions such as dementia, intoxication, sadness, and lack of motivation, anxiety disorder, or clinical depression. It should be taken into consideration that these all categories are very different from each other. Women's mental health is the important part in women's overall development and well-being. A woman having a very good mental health can contribute a lot in the overall development of family and the whole society.

If a woman is suffering from poor mental health condition, it will adversely impact her life and can also make a tremendous impact for participating fully in social and cultural life, it will be difficult for her to perform well at work and have a healthy relationship. Women's Mental Health awareness is very essential for helping and supporting women facing the various challenges of poor mental health. It is important for women and every family member to understand how to maintain a good mental health and progress.

Cognitive, Emotional and Psychological these are some types of mental health. If women suffering from any mental health problem It is very essential that time to focus on mental and physical well-being. It will be helpful to lead a positive and well-balanced life. It is the need of the time that every woman has to focus on a good mental health which will be beneficial for family and the whole society.

Ways to overcome and maintain mental health of women

Mental health poses unique challenges for women which forces them to adapt to new purposes and challenges. It is the fact that a woman's body is found changing throughout her life. Puberty, family atmosphere, friend circle, social and cultural norms, marriage, pregnancy and [childbirth](#), menopause are some of these changes that can trigger mental conditions specifically to women.

Mental health status and physical health status are both related to each other. A healthy lifestyle will help to improve women's mental as well as physical health. This includes eating a nutritious diet, avoiding bad habits, and exercise practice to enjoy healthy lifestyle.

A Woman having a good mental health can experience and response happiness, sadness, anger, excitement and all emotions in healthy ways. A Good mental health is not being happy all the time.it is also about to manage your life challenges and your relationships with others which has direct effect on our daily life. Various good physical habits, family and social surrounding helps to build good mental health. All women should focus on planning and implementing a unique strategy for themselves to manage their mental health based on their areas of interests. If women want to live a happy and fulfilled life they should focus on their friends and family, and can make a positive contribution to upcoming generations and society. As it is essential to keep ourselves in good mental health condition some things must be practiced

- Getting at least 15 minutes of sunshine per day, which will boost vitamin D and elevate mood.
- Spending half an hour in nature regularly which will fade away negative thoughts.
- Planning of short trips to rejuvenate self.
- Forgiveness plays an important role in maintaining a good mental health and life satisfaction.
- Expressing gratitude towards the useful things and people in your life.
- Participating in various activities according to the area of interest.
- Learning and practicing new life skills

- Adapting quick change in life.
 - Keeping yourself always ready for unexpected and sudden changes in life.
 - Building strong and healthy relationships with other people.
 - Planning and implementing physical and mental Exercise schedule regularly.
 - Keeping a healthy touch with family and friends and making new friends.
 - Working with proper aim and management.
 - Getting proper sleep and relaxation.
 - Thinking and behaving positively and avoiding negative thoughts and feelings.
- By imbibing these healthy habits will certainly help in improving mental health.

Innovative ways to keep away mental health problems

Women's mental health can be kept better, after witnessing specific disorders it is mandatory to seek expert's advice, without discussing the problems there is no cure, counselors can play an important role in recognizing and treating such disorders. It is the need of time that women must get such type of help. To maintain good mental health, it is important to get into some good habits that include both physical and mental actions. Too often women get bogged down in busy lives or they put others before themselves. One thing each and every woman should know that they have to take charge of their own life and mental health. For that need to take out some time from hectic schedule.

Self-role in keeping mental health

Each woman should take care of seven self-care pillars which are mental, social, emotional, physical, spiritual, environmental and recreational.

Role of family

Family plays an important role in keeping good mental health of women. Every family member should play a vital role in giving support and helping women to understand themselves.

With the help and support of family members mental disorders can be kept away.

Role of working place atmosphere

Working place atmosphere creates a huge impact on the mental health of women. Working women often face various types of mental problems. Understanding the working culture and nurturing a healthy working atmosphere will help women to keep away mental problems. Proper working culture will help in reducing some mental problems.

Role of government

Government can play a vital role in promoting a supportive environment and care for all by using various media platforms in the form of audio-visual creative material on managing stress and mental health. On 10th October 2022 government of India has launched 'National Tele Mental Health Programme', to improve the access to mental care services and mental health counselling in the country.

Conclusion

Women's health issues are crucial to overall health. It's vital to take care of themselves by seeking regular check-ups and screenings, following a healthy lifestyle and seeking professional help when needed. By empowering themselves with knowledge and seeking expert advice, they can overcome common health issues and lead healthy and fulfilling lives.

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